

SINGLE BOLT TENSION JOINT TESTS ON PULTRUDED GRP WF-SECTION WEB AND FLANGE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

Tests on 63 symmetric, double-lap, single bolt tension joints are described. The joint material was EXTREN™ 500 series pultruded GRP WF-section. 10mm and 12mm diameter bolts were used. They were torqued to 3Nm. The joints were tested parallel to the pultrusion axis and the load-extension response was recorded. The principal geometric parameters, E/D and W/D, were varied systematically and a statistical analysis was carried out on the initial damage loads to allow design data for specific confidence levels to be specified in terms of the geometric parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Pultrusion [1] is an efficient process for manufacturing long-fibre reinforced plastic structural profiles which are finding increasing use in the construction industry. The current range of profiles, produced by the major US pultrusion companies, is similar to steel profiles. The companies publish design handbooks [2 & 3] for engineers engaged in the design of pultruded frame structures.

The stiffness of pultruded GRP profiles is low, but their strength is similar to mild steel. Consequently, stiffness often governs design. In frame structures the profiles are joined by bolts, adhesives or both. Frame behaviour is not only dependent upon member stiffness and strength, but also upon the same joint attributes.

Composite joints for aerospace applications, have been the subject of intense research. Most of it has been concerned with carbon-epoxy laminates and useful summaries of the research are available [4-6]. Less research has been carried out on glass-epoxy laminates. Some of the latter research may be useful for non-aerospace applications. The need for research on pultruded GRP joint behaviour remains, because fibre architectures, resin formulations and production quality control standards and procedures are different with these materials. Moreover, in the construction industry, where pultruded GRP profiles are likely to find considerable application, joint geometry, loading conditions and the basic design philosophy are also different

Recently, researchers began to recognise that guidance provided in [2 & 3] was barely adequate for joint design in pultruded GRP materials. Independent data and guidance is needed to promote the wider use of these construction materials. At Lancaster ultimate strength testing of pultruded

GRP joints began in 1988. Similar investigations have been reported in [7 - 10]. Very limited test data and analysis are given in [7]. Extensive test data for double lap, single bolt tension joints in structural grade flat sheet material of 9.4, 12.5 and 19.2mm thickness is given in [8 & 9]. The investigation reported in [10] is concerned primarily with tension joints in custom grade flat sheet. It does, however, include detailed finite element analyses of joint behaviour. In [11], the authors report on a series of 81 joint tests on the same material as in [8], but of 6.4mm thickness. Design data for joint capacity, stiffness and end distance/ joint width are given in the paper.

This present paper extends the work in [11] to single bolt tension joint tests on material cut from the webs and flanges of two sizes of pultruded GRP WF-section.

JOINT MATERIAL

The material used in the joint tests was cut, in the form of rectangular strips, from the webs and flanges of EXTREN™ 500 series WF-section. The sections are manufactured by Morrison Molded Fiber Glass (MMFG) of Bristol, Virginia. Two sizes of section, viz 102x102x6.4 (breadth x depth x thickness; all dimensions in mm) and 203x203x9.5 WF-section, were used as the source material. Both sections have similar volume fractions of E-glass fibre, polyester resin and filler (including voids). Resin burn-off tests showed these to be 37%, 57% and 6% respectively. The E-glass reinforcement is in two forms, viz. rovings [uni-directional material] and CFM (Continuous Filament Mat) [isotropic material]. However, the fibre architectures of the two sections differ. In the smaller section it comprises: three roving layers sandwiched between four CFM layers. The rovings in the outer layers are essentially continuous, whereas they are spaced in the inner layer. At the inner layer web-flange junction, these rovings form a triangular wedge (which may account for the low strength of the junction). The fibre architecture of the larger section comprises: four roving layers sandwiched between six CFM layers (the outer two being thicker than the inner four). Again, the outer roving layers are continuous and the inner is spaced. Both sections are encased in a thin polyester veil to provide a smooth surface for handling.

JOINT GEOMETRY, TEST SET UP AND PROCEDURE

Single bolt double lap joints were tested where the inner leaf was the pultruded GRP web/flange strip and the outer leaves were machined steel plates. Two bolt sizes were chosen as being representative of those used in practice. 10mm diameter mild steel bolts were used in the web material from the smaller WF-section and 12mm bolts were used in the web and flange material of the larger section. In all tests the bolts were torqued to 3Nm. This torque simulates the lightly clamped condition which is the appropriate condition for design [11].

The purpose of the joint tests was to generate load capacity and stiffness design data. To achieve this the joints were tested in tension for a range of E/D (edge distance to bolt diameter) and W/D (inner leaf width to bolt diameter) ratios ranging from 2 to 8. Three nominally identical joints were tested for each set of E/D and W/D parameters. Fig.1 shows the joint test set up. Contact between the outer steel plates and the inner PFRP (Pultruded Fibre Reinforced Plastic) was maintained over the entire end distance and width of the joint. This ensures that the joint test resembles as closely as possible the insitu application.

Each joint was tested to failure in an Amsler universal testing machine at a load rate of 10kN/minute. The applied load and bolt head movement were recorded at 1 second intervals to provide a complete history of the joint behaviour.

Figure 1. Test fixture for double lap single bolt tension joints

Figure 2. Typical load versus bolt displacement behaviour

Figure 3(a). Failure load versus E/D ratio

Figure 3(b). Failure load versus W/D ratio

Table 1: Tension joint test data (102x102x6.4 WF-section)

W/D	E/D	Average Failure Load (kN)	-Average Damage Load (kN)	Typical Failure Mode	Average Joint Stiffness (kN/mm)
8.0	2.0	14.4	-	Shear	33.2
8.0	4.0	25.8	21.1	Shear	41.0
8.0	6.0	29.1	20.5	Bearing	38.6
8.0	8.0	28.7	21.5	Bearing	41.0
2.0	6.0	12.8	-	Tension	19.3
4.0	6.0	26.7	21.6	Bearing	32.4
6.0	6.0	27.0	18.6	Bearing	38.6

Table 2: Tension joint test data (203x203x9.5 WF-section)

Section Part	W/D	E/D	Average Failure Load (kN)	Average Damage Load (kN)	Typical Failure Mode	Average Joint Stiffness (kN/mm)
Web	8.0	2.0	27.4	-	Shear	58.2
Web	8.0	4.0	48.7	40.0	Shear	70.9
Web	8.0	6.0	55.8	40.9	Bearing	81.5
Web	8.0	8.0	50.8	38.4	Bearing	74.9
Web	2.0	8.0	21.6	-	Tension	35.1
Web	4.0	8.0	53.3	41.4	Tension	56.0
Web	6.0	8.0	57.2	41.9	Bearing	67.4
Flange	7.0	2.0	26.7	-	Shear	51.7
Flange	7.0	4.0	44.5	41.1	Shear	61.3
Flange	7.0	6.0	55.2	41.0	Bearing	64.8
Flange	7.0	8.0	55.6	40.9	Bearing	65.4
Flange	2.0	8.0	25.6	-	Tension	36.9
Flange	4.0	8.0	48.1	37.8	Tension	51.2
Flange	6.0	8.0	52.9	40.9	Bearing	66.8

Table 3: Damage design loads (% confidence levels) derived from tension joint tests

Material	Damage Design Loads (kN)			
	50%	90%	95%	99%
102*102*6.35 WF Section	20.7	18.9	18.3	17.4
203*203*9.53 WF Section	40.5	37.2	36.3	34.6

DISCUSSION OF TENSION JOINT TEST RESULTS

A typical load - extension plot is shown in Fig.2. It is evident that some movement occurs at zero load. This is denoted as the *settling distance* and ranged from 0mm to 0.3mm even though close tolerance holes were used. Once load transfer begins, the load - displacement response is linear either up to failure, or (as in Fig.2), until the *irreversible damage* load is reached. Thereafter, the joint stiffness reduces gradually until the ultimate load is reached. This type of behaviour was observed in joints where the geometric ratios, E/D and W/D, were marginally smaller or greater than the critical values. The *damage* load is associated with the initiation of bearing failure, as demonstrated in [11].

Details of the average failure loads, *damage* loads, stiffnesses and typical failure modes are given in Tables 1 and 2 for the smaller and larger WF-section material respectively.

EFFECTS OF E/D AND W/D ON JOINT CAPACITY AND FAILURE MODE

The effect of varying the E/D ratio on the joint capacity is shown in Fig.3(a) for wide joints ($W/D \geq 7$). The load capacity increases in a reasonably linear fashion until the *critical* E/D ratio is reached and thereafter remains approximately constant. The *critical* ratio corresponds to a change to the bearing failure mode. For the 6.4mm web material the *critical* value is between 4 and 6 and for the 9.5mm web and flange material it is about 6.

Likewise, the effect of varying the W/D ratio is shown in Fig.3(b) for joints with large end distances ($E/D \geq 6$). Again, the form of the curves is similar to those in Fig.3(a) and *critical* W/D values may be associated with a change to the bearing failure mode. These values are about 4 for the 6.4mm web material and between 4 and 6 for the 9.5mm web and flange material.

EFFECTS OF E/D AND W/D ON INITIAL JOINT STIFFNESS

The initial joint stiffness has been determined from the slope of the load - extension plot between the onset of loading and the *initial damage* point (see Fig.2). The stiffnesses as functions of E/D and W/D have been plotted (not shown here for lack of space) for the 6.4mm and 9.5mm thick materials respectively. These show that axial stiffness is much more sensitive to W/D than E/D. For $E/D > 2$, the axial stiffness is constant. However, as W/D increases the axial stiffness increases.

DESIGN GUIDANCE FOR SINGLE BOLT TENSION JOINTS

The tension joint tests have shown that bearing is a desirable failure mode, because it develops gradually and is associated with large deformations. The *initial damage* load signals the start of bearing failure and stiffness reduction and, moreover, is significantly lower than the ultimate load capacity of the joint. It seems an ideal load upon which to base the design load capacity of tension joints. Hence, a statistical analysis of the *initial damage* loads was undertaken to define design loads with the confidence levels shown in Table 3. Some of this data is included in load versus E/D and W/D graphs [see Figs.4(a) and 4(b) for 6.4mm material and Figs.4(c) and 4(d) for 9.5mm material]. The ultimate and *initial damage* loads for the joints are also shown on these figures. The horizontal part of the bilinear design curves is associated with bearing failure (the 50% and 95% confidence lines are shown in these figures). The inclined line, associated with shear or tension

Figure 4(a). Load versus E/D ratio (102x102x6.4 WF-section)

Figure 4(b). Load versus W/D ratio (102x102x6.4 WF-section)

Figure 4(c). Load versus E/D ratio (203x203x9.5 WF-section)

Figure 4(d). Load versus W/D ratio (203x203x9.5 WF-section)

failure modes, is drawn from the points [0.5, 0] and [1, 0] to the average failure load at the critical geometric ratio.

From the design charts, i.e. Figs.4(a) - 4(d), it is possible to recommend a range of E/D and W/D values and design load capacities for single bolt tension joints in these materials. These recommendations are compared in Table 4 with similar values taken from the manufacturer's design handbook [2].

Table 4: Comparison of bearing strengths derived from tension joint tests with manufacturer's data

Material	E/D	W/D	Design Load (kN)	Bearing Strength (N/mm ²)
102*102*6.35 WF Section (MMFG)	2-4.5 (3) ¹	3-7 (4) ¹	14.0 ²	210
203*203*9.53 WF Section (MMFG)	2-4.5 (3) ¹	3-7 (4) ¹	24.0 ³	210
102*102*6.35mm WF Section	4	4	18.3	288 ⁴
203*203*9.53mm WF Section	4	4	36.3	317 ⁵

- 1) Commonly used values from manufacturer's data (MMFG [2])
- 2) Calculated by taking the bearing strength of the material and multiplying by area of bolt in contact with specimen (6.35*10)
- 3) Calculated by taking the bearing strength of the material and multiplying by area of bolt in contact with specimen (9.53*12)
- 4) Calculated by taking the design load and dividing by the area of bolt in contact with the specimen (6.35*10)
- 5) Calculated by taking the design load and dividing by the area of bolt in contact with the specimen (9.53*12)

CONCLUSIONS

63 tests on double lap, single bolt tension joints have been carried out. The inner leaves of the joint were cut from the web of a 102x102x6.4 and the web and flanges of a 203x203x9.5 EXTRENTM 500 series WF-section. 10mm and 12mm diameter mild steel bolts were used with the 6.4mm and 9.5mm thick GRP joints respectively. The joints were tested to failure and their load - extension response was recorded for a range of E/D and W/D values.

The load - extension data showed that up to 0.3mm of extension could arise before the joint accepted load. It was also observed that joints with low E/D and W/D ratios, which failed in the tension, shear or cleavage modes, exhibited a linear response (stiffness) and failure occurred without warning. The response of those joints with geometric ratios marginally less or greater than the critical values was markedly different in as much as the load - extension response was linear up to a certain load and then the stiffness reduced and remained at that lower level until the ultimate capacity of the joint was reached. The load at which the stiffness change occurred was designated the *damage* load and, in accordance with [11], is identified as being associated with the onset of bearing failure - a desirable failure mode because it develops gradually and is associated with large deformations.

Stiffness versus E/D and W/D plots (not shown) indicated that when E/D > 2 the stiffness is independent of this parameter and that stiffness increases as the W/D ratio increases.

Load capacities with specified confidence levels, based on a statistical analysis of the *initial damage* loads, have been produced for the bearing failure mode. This data has been amalgamated with data for the other failure modes to form bilinear load capacity design charts for these joints.

Recommendations for minimum E/D and W/D ratios have also been provided to ensure failure in the benign bearing mode.

The design load capacities and recommended joint geometries have been compared with the manufacturer's data.

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